

COVER SHEET FOR PROPOSAL TO THE NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION

PROGRAM ANNOUNCEMENT/SOLICITATION NO./CLOSING DATE/if not in response to a program announcement/solicitation enter NSF 02-2					FOR NSF USE ONLY	
FOR CONSIDERATION BY NSF ORGANIZATION UNIT(S) (Indicate the most specific unit known, i.e. program, division, etc.)					NSF PROPOSAL NUMBER	
OPP - ARCTIC RESRCH SUPPRT & LOGISTI					0215512	
DATE RECEIVED	NUMBER OF COPIES	DIVISION ASSIGNED	FUND CODE	DUNS# (Data Universal Numbering System)	FILE LOCATION	
				796268548		
EMPLOYER IDENTIFICATION NUMBER (EIN) OR TAXPAYER IDENTIFICATION NUMBER (TIN)		SHOW PREVIOUS AWARD NO. IF THIS IS <input type="checkbox"/> A RENEWAL <input type="checkbox"/> AN ACCOMPLISHMENT-BASED RENEWAL 0101279		IS THIS PROPOSAL BEING SUBMITTED TO ANOTHER FEDERAL AGENCY? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> IF YES, LIST ACRONYM(S)		
NAME OF ORGANIZATION TO WHICH AWARD SHOULD BE MADE Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.			ADDRESS OF AWARDEE ORGANIZATION, INCLUDING 9 DIGIT ZIP CODE Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. 3535 College Road, Suite 101 Fairbanks, AK. 997093710			
AWARDEE ORGANIZATION CODE (IF KNOWN) 5300001191						
NAME OF PERFORMING ORGANIZATION, IF DIFFERENT FROM ABOVE			ADDRESS OF PERFORMING ORGANIZATION, IF DIFFERENT, INCLUDING 9 DIGIT ZIP CODE			
PERFORMING ORGANIZATION CODE (IF KNOWN)						
IS AWARDEE ORGANIZATION (Check All That Apply) (See GPG II.C For Definitions) <input type="checkbox"/> FOR-PROFIT ORGANIZATION <input type="checkbox"/> SMALL BUSINESS <input type="checkbox"/> MINORITY BUSINESS <input type="checkbox"/> WOMAN-OWNED BUSINESS						
TITLE OF PROPOSED PROJECT Organizational Support to the U.S. Arctic Science Program						
REQUESTED AMOUNT \$ 559,850	PROPOSED DURATION (1-60 MONTHS) 0 months	REQUESTED STARTING DATE	SHOW RELATED PREPROPOSAL NO., IF APPLICABLE			
CHECK APPROPRIATE BOX(ES) IF THIS PROPOSAL INCLUDES ANY OF THE ITEMS LISTED BELOW						
<input type="checkbox"/> BEGINNING INVESTIGATOR (GPG I.A) <input type="checkbox"/> HUMAN SUBJECTS (GPG II.C.11) <input type="checkbox"/> DISCLOSURE OF LOBBYING ACTIVITIES (GPG II.C) Exemption Subsection _____ or IRB App. Date _____ <input type="checkbox"/> PROPRIETARY & PRIVILEGED INFORMATION (GPG I.B, II.C.6) <input type="checkbox"/> INTERNATIONAL COOPERATIVE ACTIVITIES: COUNTRY/COUNTRIES INVOLVED (GPG II.C.9) <input type="checkbox"/> HISTORIC PLACES (GPG II.C.9) <input type="checkbox"/> SMALL GRANT FOR EXPLOR. RESEARCH (SGER) (GPG II.C.11) <input type="checkbox"/> VERTEBRATE ANIMALS (GPG II.C.11) IACUC App. Date _____ <input type="checkbox"/> HIGH RESOLUTION GRAPHICS/OTHER GRAPHICS WHERE EXACT COLOR REPRESENTATION IS REQUIRED FOR PROPER INTERPRETATION (GPG I.E.1)						
PI/PD DEPARTMENT ARCUS		PI/PD POSTAL ADDRESS 3535 College Road, Suite 101				
PI/PD FAX NUMBER 907-474-1604		Fairbanks, AK 997093710 United States				
NAMES (TYPED)	High Degree	Yr of Degree	Telephone Number	Electronic Mail Address		
PI/PD NAME Wendy K Warnick	HS	1973	907-474-1600	warnick@arcus.org		
CO-PI/PD						
CO-PI/PD						
CO-PI/PD						
CO-PI/PD						

CERTIFICATION PAGE

Certification for Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant:

By signing and submitting this proposal, the individual applicant or the authorized official of the applicant institution is: (1) certifying that statements made herein are true and complete to the best of his/her knowledge; and (2) agreeing to accept the obligation to comply with NSF award terms and conditions if an award is made as a result of this application. Further, the applicant is hereby providing certifications regarding debarment and suspension, drug-free workplace, and lobbying activities (see below), as set forth in Grant Proposal Guide (GPG), NSF 02-2. Willful provision of false information in this application and its supporting documents or in reports required under an ensuing award is a criminal offense (U. S. Code, Title 18, Section 1001).

In addition, if the applicant institution employs more than fifty persons, the authorized official of the applicant institution is certifying that the institution has implemented a written and enforced conflict of interest policy that is consistent with the provisions of Grant Policy Manual Section 510; that to the best of his/her knowledge, all financial disclosures required by that conflict of interest policy have been made; and that all identified conflicts of interest will have been satisfactorily managed, reduced or eliminated prior to the institution's expenditure of any funds under the award, in accordance with the institution's conflict of interest policy. Conflicts which cannot be satisfactorily managed, reduced or eliminated must be disclosed to NSF.

Drug Free Work Place Certification

By electronically signing the NSF Proposal Cover Sheet, the Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant is providing the Drug Free Work Place Certification contained in Appendix A of the Grant Proposal Guide.

Debarment and Suspension Certification

(If answer "yes", please provide explanation.)

Is the organization or its principals presently debarred, suspended, proposed for debarment, declared ineligible, or voluntarily excluded from covered transactions by any Federal department or agency?

Yes

No

By electronically signing the NSF Proposal Cover Sheet, the Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant is providing the Debarment and Suspension Certification contained in Appendix B of the Grant Proposal Guide.

Certification Regarding Lobbying

This certification is required for an award of a Federal contract, grant, or cooperative agreement exceeding \$100,000 and for an award of a Federal loan or a commitment providing for the United States to insure or guarantee a loan exceeding \$150,000.

Certification for Contracts, Grants, Loans and Cooperative Agreements

The undersigned certifies, to the best of his or her knowledge and belief, that:

(1) No federal appropriated funds have been paid or will be paid, by or on behalf of the undersigned, to any person for influencing or attempting to influence an officer or employee of any agency, a Member of Congress, an officer or employee of Congress, or an employee of a Member of Congress in connection with the awarding of any federal contract, the making of any Federal grant, the making of any Federal loan, the entering into of any cooperative agreement, and the extension, continuation, renewal, amendment, or modification of any Federal contract, grant, loan, or cooperative agreement.

(2) If any funds other than Federal appropriated funds have been paid or will be paid to any person for influencing or attempting to influence an officer or employee of any agency, a Member of Congress, an officer or employee of Congress, or an employee of a Member of Congress in connection with this Federal contract, grant, loan, or cooperative agreement, the undersigned shall complete and submit Standard Form-LLL, "Disclosure of Lobbying Activities," in accordance with its instructions.

(3) The undersigned shall require that the language of this certification be included in the award documents for all subawards at all tiers including subcontracts, subgrants, and contracts under grants, loans, and cooperative agreements and that all subrecipients shall certify and disclose accordingly.

This certification is a material representation of fact upon which reliance was placed when this transaction was made or entered into. Submission of this certification is a prerequisite for making or entering into this transaction imposed by section 1352, Title 31, U.S. Code. Any person who fails to file the required certification shall be subject to a civil penalty of not less than \$10,000 and not more than \$100,000 for each such failure.

AUTHORIZED ORGANIZATIONAL REPRESENTATIVE		SIGNATURE	DATE
NAME Wendy K Warnick		No Signature Required Electronic Signature	Jan 21 2002 1:55AM
TELEPHONE NUMBER 907-474-1600	ELECTRONIC MAIL ADDRESS warnick@arcus.org	FAX NUMBER 907-474-1604	

*SUBMISSION OF SOCIAL SECURITY NUMBERS IS VOLUNTARY AND WILL NOT AFFECT THE ORGANIZATION'S ELIGIBILITY FOR AN AWARD. HOWEVER, THEY ARE AN INTEGRAL PART OF THE INFORMATION SYSTEM AND ASSIST IN PROCESSING THE PROPOSAL. SSN SOLICITED UNDER NSF ACT OF 1950, AS AMENDED.

SUMMARY OF PROPOSED WORK

This is a request for a supplement to ARCUS' cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation (No. OPP-0101279). The supplement of \$559,850 will support six new activities and will provide additional funding for four ongoing activities as part of the organizational support ARCUS provides to the U.S. Arctic science programs. Several of the projects described here provide editorial and publication support or preparation and distribution of information to assist NSF and the arctic research community. Other activities require more complex community planning processes and creation of a variety of resources.

This request does not include a description of all projects that require a small amount of increased funding for successful implementation. Savings in other activities in the same general category will offset small increases in funding necessary to support several projects. Examples include the cost of developing an online survey process and interactive database for the ALIAS web site, which will be offset by savings in travel for the Arctic Logistics project, made possible by holding meetings of the Research Support and Logistics Working Group by teleconference and in conjunction with other scientific research meetings. Another example is the increased management cost of the popular and effective Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series, offset by savings in Arctic Science Education activities, achieved through productive partnerships with other organizations that have provided more collaborative support for joint projects than anticipated.

The proposed activities that require supplemental funding are summarized below. Activities not previously included in this cooperative agreement are marked *New*. All of the activities support the community science planning process for the NSF Arctic Sciences Section or provide information and support for the conduct of Arctic research.

ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1. *New* Revision and Reprinting of the SEARCH Brochure

The brochure for *SEARCH: The Study of Environmental Arctic Change*, originally published by ARCUS for the SEARCH Interagency Working Group and the Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee in March 2001, will be revised and 2,000 copies printed.

ARCTIC SYSTEM SCIENCE PROGRAM COORDINATION

2. ARCSS All-Hands Workshop 2002

Funding for the 2002 ARCSS Program All-Hands workshop, the second ARCSS-wide workshop for ARCSS-funded investigators, was originally included in the second-year budget of ARCUS' cooperative agreement with NSF but, because of the workshop schedule, the activities will take place during the first year of the agreement, in February 2002. In addition to moving funds from year two to year one, the supplemental funds requested here will provide participant support for undergraduate and graduate students funded through the ARCSS Program to attend the workshop. Strong participation of young researchers at the workshop will support the development of a cohort of researchers familiar with interdisciplinary and integrative arctic research, as well as insuring the infusion of new ideas and approaches into the science planning process. We expect 250-300 total participants at this workshop.

3. CHAMP: *The Hydrologic Cycle and its Role in Arctic and Global Environmental Change: A Rationale and Strategy for Synthesis Study*

In 2001, ARCUS worked with the Arctic Hydrology Science Steering Committee (SSC) and workshop participants to prepare the report *The Hydrologic Cycle and its Role in Arctic and Global Environmental Change: A Rationale and Strategy for Synthesis Study*, leading to the development of a new research initiative for a *pan-Arctic Community-wide Hydrological Analysis and Monitoring Program* or CHAMP. After the completion and distribution of the report, ARCUS was asked by the SSC to prepare additional materials and resources derived from the report and the planning process to inform the community about this research initiative. Supplemental funds requested here will support the development of two versions of a poster and two versions of a computer-based informational presentation.

ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION

4. *New Planning for a Community Conference on Arctic Social Sciences Research*

ARCUS will follow the recommendations from the January 2001 workshop on arctic social sciences to work with the research community to plan a large community-wide conference in late 2002. Coordination activities include the development of a web site and other online resources to communicate the recommendations of the workshops, and to promote discussion with science steering committees, workshop chairs, working group leaders, other key participants, and members of the research community to identify critical areas and research priorities for further discussion.

5. *New Publication of Frontiers in Polar Social Sciences: Indigenous Observations of Environmental Change*

ARCUS proposes to publish a volume tentatively titled *Indigenous Observations of Environmental Change*, edited by Igor Krupnik of the Arctic Studies Centre of the Smithsonian Institution and Dyanna Jolly of the Centre for Maori and Indigenous Planning and Development, Lincoln University, New Zealand. The volume will consist of 10 papers of between 35 and 55 pages each, together comprising a comprehensive summary of ongoing efforts to document indigenous perspectives of climate change in the Arctic. The papers will include photographs, line drawings, and illustrations.

The international collection of articles will review major individual studies undertaken during the last few years, primarily in North America. Each contribution will be formatted as a comprehensive project summary, with references, appendices, and illustrations. The publication will offer the first comparative survey of research practices and paradigms used in current indigenous knowledge documentation studies as well as general assessment of the field and of the data collected. The summary will serve as a networking and communication tool, bringing together research on indigenous knowledge and climate change into one volume. ARCUS will make it available to arctic scientists, northern communities, and international agencies. ARCUS will do the layout and prepare the volume for printing, coordinate the pre-press and printing process, and manage distribution for the 1,500 copies printed. The editors will handle communications with the individual authors.

ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

6. *New Arctic Science Education Report*

ARCUS convened a 15-member working group of selected researchers, educators, students, and arctic community representatives in March 2000 to review various programs and educational approaches to science education and to prepare recommendations for the development of research-experience-based science education programs for the Arctic. The previous ARCUS cooperative agreement with NSF funded development of the report and circulation of the draft for community review. The supplemental funding requested here will support the completion of the report based on contributions and comments from reviewers and the publication and distribution of 600 copies, as well as making the report and its recommendations available electronically through the ARCUS web site.

INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

7. *New Publication: The Arctic*

Many members of the arctic research community have expressed a need for an introduction to the environments and peoples of the Arctic that is scientifically accurate while remaining comprehensible to the general public, including middle and high school students. To address this need, ARCUS began developing an overview of the arctic region for a general audience in 2001, with funding through our previous cooperative agreement with NSF. Tentatively titled *The Arctic: Changes in a Polar Region*, this book will be similar to a magazine in quality of graphics and level of complexity and will be accessible to a wide range of readers. The contents and the publication design and layout are targeted to the general public and middle and high school students. The contents cover ocean, terrestrial, and human components of the Arctic and review various aspects of these domains, including contemporary and historical research, through a seasonal framework. Links among important arctic processes and between the biophysical systems and human cultures are illustrated. The draft publication was circulated for review in January 2001 by a selected group of educators, arctic researchers, and experts in science information development. The reviews provided substantive guidance for the difficult task of describing diverse and complex processes and simply and clearly. Because of the amount of work still required to create a publication of the quality considered necessary by ARCUS, NSF, and the research community, we delayed further work on this publication in order to direct staff resources to other more urgently needed projects. This supplemental funding requested here will support the completion of this important resource and the publication and distribution of 5,000 copies.

8. *Directory of Arctic Researchers*

The supplemental funds requested here will support the ongoing expansion and development of the on-line *Directory of Arctic Researchers*, including revisions in the programming of the database functions to improve search capabilities, to create interactive on-line submission to the directory database, and to integrate the database information and search functions more fully with the ALIAS web site. The *Directory* currently contains entries for 3,423 Arctic researchers.

9. Arctic Community Outreach

Ongoing Arctic outreach activities include the development of information resources regarding arctic research activities, needs, and priorities and participation in outreach activities at upcoming scientific meetings or workshops to inform the broader scientific community and key policy and decisions-makers about important arctic research efforts and findings. The supplemental funds requested here also will partially support the preparation and publication of the abstract volume from the *Arctic Forum 2001*.

10. *New* Consultation on Federally Funded Research in Northern Alaska

Section 7 of the Endangered Species Act requires Federal agencies to "consult" with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) on any actions that might affect species listed as "threatened" or "endangered." Federal agencies conducting or funding research activities must consult with the USFWS on the potential impacts to listed species. In northern Alaska, there are two species of sea duck, the spectacled eider (*Somateria fischeri*) and Steller's eider (*Polysticta stelleri*) that may be affected by the activities associated with scientific research of all kinds. Consultation is a process undertaken jointly by the "action agency" and the USFWS, although the action agency may designate another party to conduct the consultation with the USFWS. As an agency awarding Federal grant monies, the National Science Foundation (NSF) is obligated to consult with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service regarding the impacts of proposed scientific research (of any type) on threatened or endangered species.

ARCUS will prepare information providing guidance to NSF and to researchers funded by NSF on the requirements for consultation with USFWS regarding the potential impacts of their research on listed species. The materials will inform researchers about the species in question, the critical time periods, and geographic areas of concern and will guide researchers and NSF program managers through a decision-making process to help them determine what level of consultation is required, how to initiate the consultation process, and who to contact for further information. The materials will be made available as a downloadable PDF linked from various web sites providing research support and logistics information to arctic researchers, as well as being available as a photocopied handout.

SUMMARY

ARCUS has facilitated scientific planning for arctic research efforts for over ten years by working with the scientific community through surveys, workshops, Internet communications, and other means to define science priorities and research initiatives. ARCUS has organized dozens of workshops and published numerous scientific planning documents, which reflect the recommendations of the arctic research community on scientific priorities in various research fields. All of the activities described in this request for supplemental funds support the community science planning process for the NSF Arctic Sciences Section and provide information and support for the conduct of Arctic research and, therefore, will contribute to the overall excellence and advancement of arctic research supported by the National Science Foundation.

JUSTIFICATION FOR THE SUPPLEMENT

This is a request for a supplement to ARCUS' cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation (No. OPP-0101279). The supplement of \$559,850 to the original funding awarded through No. OPP-0101279 is necessary because:

1. Several activities described in this request are new and require work beyond what was covered in the initial funding to ARCUS;
2. One major activity, the all-investigator workshop for the NSF Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program, was originally included in the second-year budget of the cooperative agreement but, because of the workshop schedule, the activities will take place during the first year of the agreement, in February 2002;
3. An increase in the duration or level of activity in several ongoing projects requires additional funding.

All of the activities described here are in keeping with and part of ARCUS' work for the National Science Foundation (NSF), providing organizational support for the U.S. arctic science programs.

ARCUS is submitting this supplement request to undertake the new or additional activities at the request of and on behalf of several community-based science steering committees—the ARCSS Advisory Committee, the ARCSS Program's Land-Atmosphere-Ice Interactions and Ocean-Atmosphere-Ice Interactions science steering committees, and the Arctic Hydrology Science Steering Committee. Other tasks are proposed in response to requests from the arctic social sciences research community, the SEARCH Interagency Working Group, and the Arctic Science Education Working Group. The specific activities and the support that will be provided have been discussed with the relevant NSF Program Managers as well.

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET YEAR 1

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY				
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)			
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted		
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-mos.			Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
				CAL	ACAD	SUMR		
1. Wendy K Warnick - none				0.43	0.00	0.00	\$ 2,882	\$
2.								
3.								
4.								
5.								
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)				0.00	0.00	0.00	0	
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)				0.43	0.00	0.00	2,882	
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)								
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES				0.00	0.00	0.00	0	
2. (2) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)				8.50	0.00	0.00	33,329	
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS							0	
4. (2) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS							1,867	
5. (0) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)							0	
6. (0) OTHER							0	
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)							38,078	
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)							16,025	
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)							54,103	
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)								
TOTAL EQUIPMENT							0	
E. TRAVEL 1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							324	
2. FOREIGN							1,183	
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS								
1. STIPENDS \$ 10,500								
2. TRAVEL 50,385								
3. SUBSISTENCE 63,365								
4. OTHER 0								
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (0) TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS							124,250	
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS								
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES							19,561	
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION							28,315	
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES							52,842	
4. COMPUTER SERVICES							494	
5. SUBAWARDS							35,733	
6. OTHER							87,765	
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS							224,710	
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)							404,570	
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) Indirect (Rate: 42.1000, Base: 368837)								
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)							155,280	
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)							559,850	
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.D.7.j.)							0	
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)							\$ 559,850	\$
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$				
PI / PD TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE*			DATE	FOR NSF USE ONLY				
Wendy K Warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION				
ORG. REP. TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE*			DATE	Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG		
warnick, Wendy								

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET Cumulative

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY				
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)			
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted		
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-mos.			Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
				CAL	ACAD	SUMR		
1. Wendy K Warnick - none				0.43	0.00	0.00	\$ 2,882	\$
2.								
3.								
4.								
5.								
6. () OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)				0.00	0.00	0.00	0	
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)				0.43	0.00	0.00	2,882	
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)								
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES				0.00	0.00	0.00	0	
2. (2) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)				8.50	0.00	0.00	33,329	
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS							0	
4. (2) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS							1,867	
5. (0) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)							0	
6. (0) OTHER							0	
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)							38,078	
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)							16,025	
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)							54,103	
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)								
TOTAL EQUIPMENT							0	
E. TRAVEL 1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							324	
2. FOREIGN							1,183	
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS								
1. STIPENDS \$ 10,500								
2. TRAVEL 50,385								
3. SUBSISTENCE 63,365								
4. OTHER 0								
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (0) TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS							124,250	
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS								
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L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)							\$ 559,850	\$
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$				
PI / PD TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE*			DATE	FOR NSF USE ONLY				
Wendy K Warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION				
ORG. REP. TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE*			DATE	Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG		
warnick, Wendy								

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
OPP-0101279
Budget Explanation by Task

	5-year Budget	YEAR 1 Budget before supplement	YEAR 1 Projections Thru 3/31/02	YEAR 1 Adjustment for Supplemental Budget Request
<u>Core Support</u>				
60 CORE SUPPORT				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	990,334	174,996	163,511	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	86,808	15,770	7,734	
Travel (foreign)	12,054	2,366	-	
Participant Support Costs	-	-	167	
Other Direct Costs	<u>337,800</u>	<u>58,820</u>	<u>62,152</u>	-
Total direct costs	1,426,996	251,952	233,563	18,390
Indirect Costs	<u>600,765</u>	<u>106,072</u>	<u>98,330</u>	<u>7,742</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>2,027,761</u>	<u>358,024</u>	<u>331,892</u>	<u>26,132</u>

Arctic Community Science Planning

61 ARCTIC LOGISTICS

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	109,509	16,879	25,428	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	32,140	6,308	4,143	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	165,620	32,344	14,354	
Other Direct Costs	<u>81,168</u>	<u>4,990</u>	<u>7,660</u>	-
Total direct costs	388,437	60,521	51,584	8,937
Indirect Costs	<u>163,532</u>	<u>25,479</u>	<u>21,717</u>	<u>3,762</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>551,968</u>	<u>86,000</u>	<u>73,301</u>	<u>12,699</u>

62 ALIAS WEBSITE

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	387,761	69,082	64,423	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	80,350	15,770	14,952	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	
Other Direct Costs	<u>11,900</u>	<u>11,500</u>	<u>21,804</u>	-
Total direct costs	480,011	96,352	101,179	(4,827)
Indirect Costs	<u>202,084</u>	<u>40,564</u>	<u>42,596</u>	<u>(2,032)</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>682,095</u>	<u>136,916</u>	<u>143,776</u>	<u>(6,859)</u>

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
OPP-0101279
Budget Explanation by Task

	5-year Budget	YEAR 1 Budget before supplement	YEAR 1 Projections Thru 3/31/02	YEAR 1 Adjustment for Supplemental Budget Request
63 GIS PLANNING				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	13,282	13,282	18,434	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	-	-	631	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	7,000	7,000	8,050	
Other Direct Costs	29,800	29,800	24,450	-
Total direct costs	50,082	50,082	51,565	(1,483)
Indirect Costs	21,084	21,084	21,709	(624)
Total direct and indirect costs	71,166	71,166	73,274	(2,107)
44 SEARCH BROCHURE				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	-	1,083	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	
Other Direct Costs	-	-	3,336	-
Total direct costs	-	-	4,419	(4,419)
Indirect Costs	-	-	1,860	(1,860)
Total direct and indirect costs	-	-	6,279	(6,279)
65 WKSP TBD				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	16,536	-	-	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic and foreign)	3,204	-	-	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	31,725	-	-	
Other Direct Costs	13,450	-	-	-
Total direct costs	64,915	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	27,329	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	92,244	-	-	-

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	5-year Budget	YEAR 1 Budget before supplement	YEAR 1 Projections Thru 3/31/02	YEAR 1 Adjustment for Supplemental Budget Request
66 WKSP TBD				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	17,250	-	-	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	3,254	-	-	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	32,350	-	-	
Other Direct Costs	13,450	-	-	-
Total direct costs	66,304	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	27,914	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	94,218	-	-	-

67 WKSP TBD				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	18,117	-	-	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	3,304	-	-	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	32,975	-	-	
Other Direct Costs	13,450	-	-	-
Total direct costs	67,846	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	28,563	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	96,409	-	-	-

NSF Arctic Sciences Section Coordination

71 ARCTIC SECTION SCIENCE MATERIALS

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	13,282	13,282	13,263	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	
Other Direct Costs	11,500	11,500	11,500	-
Total direct costs	24,782	24,782	24,763	18
Indirect Costs	10,433	10,433	10,425	8
Total direct and indirect costs	35,215	35,215	35,189	26

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	5-year Budget	YEAR 1 Budget before supplement	YEAR 1 Projections Thru 3/31/02	YEAR 1 Adjustment for Supplemental Budget Request
ARCSS Program Coordination				
73 ARCSS COORDINATION				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	60,200	11,046	11,045	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	28,124	5,520	4,731	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	119,250	23,550	16,985	
Other Direct Costs	<u>18,096</u>	<u>3,698</u>	<u>4,490</u>	-
Total direct costs	225,670	43,814	37,251	6,563
Indirect Costs	<u>95,007</u>	<u>18,446</u>	<u>15,683</u>	<u>2,763</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>320,677</u>	<u>62,259</u>	<u>52,933</u>	<u>9,326</u>
74 ARCSS All-Hands Workshop				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	62,023	28,500	33,595	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	6,308	-	8,485	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	47,425	-	162,825	
Other Direct Costs	<u>31,350</u>	<u>4,250</u>	<u>108,800</u>	-
Total direct costs	147,106	32,750	313,705	(280,955)
Indirect Costs	<u>61,932</u>	<u>13,788</u>	<u>132,070</u>	<u>(118,282)</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>209,037</u>	<u>46,538</u>	<u>445,775</u>	<u>(399,237)</u>
75 HARC SMO				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	31,957	10,175	21,670	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	14,268	4,731	4,896	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	39,807	13,194	2,932	
Other Direct Costs	<u>65,948</u>	<u>21,982</u>	<u>22,332</u>	-
Total direct costs	151,980	50,082	51,831	(1,750)
Indirect Costs	<u>63,984</u>	<u>21,084</u>	<u>21,821</u>	<u>(737)</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>215,964</u>	<u>71,166</u>	<u>73,652</u>	<u>(2,486)</u>

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	5-year Budget	YEAR 1 Budget before supplement	YEAR 1 Projections Thru 3/31/02	YEAR 1 Adjustment for Supplemental Budget Request
76 ARCTIC HYDROLOGY REPORT				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	9,775	9,775	15,795	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	
Other Direct Costs	1,768	1,768	1,207	-
Total direct costs	11,543	11,543	17,001	(5,459)
Indirect Costs	4,859	4,859	7,158	(2,298)
Total direct and indirect costs	16,402	16,402	24,159	(7,757)

ASSP Program Coordination

79 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES WORKSHOP

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	15,822	-	8,524	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	3,154	-	46	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	31,100	-	-	
Other Direct Costs	13,984	-	13	-
Total direct costs	64,060	-	8,583	(8,583)
Indirect Costs	26,969	-	3,614	(3,614)
Total direct and indirect costs	91,029	-	12,197	(12,197)

80 GREENLAND BOOK

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	6,043	6,043	1,326	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	
Other Direct Costs	13,500	13,500	10,937	-
Total direct costs	19,543	19,543	12,263	7,280
Indirect Costs	8,228	8,228	5,163	3,065
Total direct and indirect costs	27,771	27,771	17,425	10,345

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	5-year Budget	YEAR 1 Budget before supplement	YEAR 1 Projections Thru 3/31/02	YEAR 1 Adjustment for Supplemental Budget Request
97 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES VOLUME				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	-	6,501	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	-	-	1,577	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	3,549	
Participant Support Costs	-	-	13,000	
Other Direct Costs	-	-	17,692	-
Total direct costs	-	-	42,319	(42,319)
Indirect Costs	-	-	17,816	(17,816)
Total direct and indirect costs	-	-	60,135	(60,135)

ANS Program Coordination

84 ANS WORKSHOP AND REPORT

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	10,193	-	-	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	
Other Direct Costs	8,300	-	-	-
Total direct costs	18,493	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	7,786	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	26,279	-	-	-

Arctic Science Education

85 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION ACTIVITIES

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	13,776	2,656	8,369	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	16,070	3,154	2,316	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	19,110	3,732	-	
Other Direct Costs	26,488	5,297	702	-
Total direct costs	75,444	14,839	11,387	3,452
Indirect Costs	31,762	6,247	4,794	1,453
Total direct and indirect costs	107,205	21,086	16,181	4,905

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	5-year Budget	YEAR 1 Budget before supplement	YEAR 1 Projections Thru 3/31/02	YEAR 1 Adjustment for Supplemental Budget Request
86 ARCTIC VISITING SPEAKERS PROGRAM				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	27,181	4,942	7,266	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	148,500	29,700	29,700	
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	<u>175,681</u>	<u>34,642</u>	<u>36,966</u>	(2,324)
Indirect Costs	<u>73,962</u>	<u>14,584</u>	<u>15,563</u>	(978)
Total direct and indirect costs	<u><u>249,643</u></u>	<u><u>49,226</u></u>	<u><u>52,528</u></u>	<u><u>(3,302)</u></u>

16 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION REPORT

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	-	9,877	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	
Other Direct Costs	-	-	17,700	-
Total direct costs	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>27,577</u>	(27,577)
Indirect Costs	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>11,610</u>	(11,610)
Total direct and indirect costs	<u><u>-</u></u>	<u><u>-</u></u>	<u><u>39,186</u></u>	<u><u>(39,187)</u></u>

Information and Outreach

90 WITNESS THE ARCTIC NEWSLETTER

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	93,344	17,033	23,699	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	8,035	1,577	1,594	
Other Direct Costs	<u>201,500</u>	<u>40,300</u>	<u>35,288</u>	-
Total direct costs	<u>302,879</u>	<u>58,910</u>	<u>60,581</u>	(1,671)
Indirect Costs	<u>127,512</u>	<u>24,801</u>	<u>25,505</u>	(703)
Total direct and indirect costs	<u><u>430,391</u></u>	<u><u>83,712</u></u>	<u><u>86,085</u></u>	<u><u>(2,374)</u></u>

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	5-year Budget	YEAR 1 Budget before supplement	YEAR 1 Projections Thru 3/31/02	YEAR 1 Adjustment for Supplemental Budget Request
91 INTERNET RESOURCES				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	372,565	67,357	55,527	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	-	-	1,402	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	
Other Direct Costs	-	-	9,947	-
Total direct costs	372,565	67,357	66,875	482
Indirect Costs	156,850	28,357	28,154	203
Total direct and indirect costs	529,414	95,714	95,030	685
92 ARCTIC INFO LISTSERVER				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	98,790	18,039	13,797	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	
Other Direct Costs	-	-	2,478	-
Total direct costs	98,790	18,039	16,275	1,764
Indirect Costs	41,591	7,594	6,852	743
Total direct and indirect costs	140,381	25,634	23,127	2,507
93 DIRECTORY OF ARCTIC RESEARCHERS				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	30,270	5,478	7,491	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	8,035	1,577	-	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	
Other Direct Costs	1,000	-	4,140	-
Total direct costs	39,305	7,055	11,631	(4,576)
Indirect Costs	16,548	2,970	4,897	(1,927)
Total direct and indirect costs	55,853	10,025	16,528	(6,503)

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	5-year Budget	YEAR 1 Budget before supplement	YEAR 1 Projections Thru 3/31/02	YEAR 1 Adjustment for Supplemental Budget Request
94 ARCTIC COMMUNITY OUTREACH				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	60,110	10,857	13,977	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	32,140	6,308	65	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	41,550	8,130	2,356	
Other Direct Costs	<u>75,090</u>	<u>15,015</u>	<u>29,533</u>	-
Total direct costs	208,890	40,310	45,930	(5,620)
Indirect Costs	<u>87,943</u>	<u>16,971</u>	<u>19,337</u>	<u>(2,366)</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>296,833</u>	<u>57,281</u>	<u>65,267</u>	<u>(7,987)</u>
95 INTERNET GRAPHICS ARCHIVE				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	33,750	-	-	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	
Other Direct Costs	<u>30,000</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct costs	63,750	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	<u>26,839</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>90,588</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
96 PUBLICATION: THE ARCTIC				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	-	7,142	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	
Other Direct Costs	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>50,970</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct costs	-	-	58,112	(58,112)
Indirect Costs	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>9,421</u>	<u>(9,421)</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>67,533</u>	<u>(67,533)</u>

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	5-year Budget	YEAR 1 Budget before supplement	YEAR 1 Projections Thru 3/31/02	YEAR 1 Adjustment for Supplemental Budget Request
98 ENDANGERED SPECIES CONSULTATION INFORMATION				
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	-	1,782	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	-	-	1,782	(1,782)
Indirect Costs	-	-	750	(750)
Total direct and indirect costs	-	-	2,532	(2,532)

TOTAL PROGRAMS

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	2,491,867	479,421	533,523	
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	
Travel (domestic)	317,159	59,138	50,977	
Travel (foreign)	12,054	2,366	3,549	
Participant Support Costs	724,447	119,227	251,962	
Other Direct Costs	999,542	222,420	447,131	-
Total direct costs	4,545,069	882,572	1,287,142	(404,570)
Indirect Costs	1,913,474	371,563	526,843	(155,280)
Total direct and indirect costs	6,458,543	1,254,135	1,813,986	(559,850)